

'Matchmaking' and 'I Bring the Idea' meetups content

D2.6 version 1.3

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The logo for the MERLIN project, featuring the word "merlin" in a lowercase, sans-serif font. A small red square is positioned to the left of the letter "m".

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Executive summary

This document, D2.6 – Matchmaking and I Bring the Idea content– is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460, and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020".

Merlin aims to foster and accelerate the transfer of knowledge from the projects funded in FP7 and H2020, be it on the form of license agreement, patent or ideally, spinoff or startup to directly exploit them, by organising practical hands-on workshops; meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors; and by attending scientific conferences to reach a wider public. The programme will equip participants with knowledge, skills and a network to generate market-led business models to unlock potential and accelerate this journey.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide the content and structure of the two kind of meetups - Matchmaking and I Bring the Idea content - that will be organized and delivered by all the members

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1. Introduction

This deliverable (D2.6), “Matchmaking and I Bring the Idea content”, is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460 and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020"¹ and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020"². The purpose of D2.6 is to provide a description of the structure, organization and purpose of the two kind of meetups that will be organized and delivered by the partners for helping MERLIN participants know and engage with the local and national ecosystem. All members of the Consortium will use the same content for conducting the workshops at their locations.

Funding in ICT project under FP7 and H2020 totals over 11.000 million € by the end of the current work programme. Stimulated and supported by these programs, many researchers in universities, institutes and SMEs have worked hard on developing new ground-breaking technologies and disruptive services. But when it comes to commercialize the results or create a company, these researchers are unsure on how to proceed. MERLIN project, funded in the context of the EC initiative *Innovation Radar*, wants to start changing this situation by organizing a set of activities aiming:

- To stimulate a greater interest in the scientific community to view their research results as potential opportunities to be exploited with the correct business model.
- To equip researchers with modern, need-first and market-led methodologies that will help them to shape their ideas and outputs into innovations to be ready for market validation and posterior commercialization.
- To introduce the rich European entrepreneurship ecosystem and the opportunities it offers to create and support startups on their journey.

Among the planned activities, it is worth highlighting the following:

- Organisation of 45 practical workshops covering state-of-the-art innovation and entrepreneurship methodologies in 8 European cities.
- Organisation of 5 workshops in scientific conferences to reach more researchers and engage them with the activities organized by MERLIN and other ICT-32 projects.
- Organisation of 8 meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors by the end of each year.
- Organisation of 4 webinars on SME growth and new business models for public-private partnership.

This document described the organization of the meetup activities, which are closely integrated with the project objective and remaining activities. Deliverable D2.6 is related to D3.1 (planning of MERLIN activities), as well as to D4.1 and D4.2 (reports on the execution of the project activities over the first and second year, respectively). The running of the first meetup event constitutes milestone MS4. Meetup participants will form the core of the community building initiative of MERLIN (WP5), and of course the meetups will be a great opportunity for performing communication activities (WP6).

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

² https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/sites/horizon2020/files/FactSheet_Open_Access.pdf

1.1. Audience

The main intended audience for this document is the MERLIN project consortium and the European Commission, but also other entrepreneurship programmes can make use of the results of D2.6 to organize their own meetups.

The target audience of the meetups are, on the one hand, researchers and startups involved in MERLIN activities, and on the other hand, diverse stakeholders of the entrepreneurship ecosystem: investors, other entrepreneurs, public institutions, incubators/accelerators, etc.

1.2. Structure

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 describes the objectives and structure of the two kind of meetups.
- Section 3 presents the pitching decks for each meetup.
- Section 4 summarizes the conclusions.

2. “Meetups” activity

As mentioned before, MERLIN aims to foster the exploitation of the research results obtained from public funded EU projects. The main activities carried out to achieve this objective are hands-on thematic workshops (regular and conference ones), but one of crucial elements of the project will be answering the needs of those innovators and researchers who are interested in the exploitation of the results of their work. Recognizing that the successful transfer of knowledge and creation of start-ups/spin-offs needs time, money, support and engagement, meetups have been planned as a very important complementary activity to the aforementioned training activities. The most outstanding and promising researchers, SMEs and startups, will receive further support regarding the development of their business plan, and will be also invited to special meetup activities. These activities, described in the next sections, will help MERLIN participants meet other people alike, will put them in contact with potential commercial partners, business angels and customers, and they will serve as a test field where they could put into practice what they have learnt on the workshops. Meetups will be a great opportunity to expand the participant’s network of contact and for getting to know their local entrepreneurial ecosystem. Besides, it will also be a good opportunity for the communicating the results of MERLIN project.

Two types of meetup activities will be planned, to help participants exploit their research results: ‘*Matchmaking*’ and ‘*I bring the idea*’ meetups. The first type of activity is for researchers who do want to get involved into the process of creating the spin-off or start-up to exploit their research results, while ‘*I bring the idea*’ is for researchers who don't, since there can be researchers who are more interested in research than in commercialization. In more detail:

- **Matchmaking events** will be organised and structured in a way that will allow researchers, innovators to directly engage with ICT industry representatives, as well as prospective customers/clients/partners. Project partners will get to know workshop participants, and their applied research and innovations through questionnaires, which will help to look for relevant industry representatives and match each researcher and innovator with the right people so that the meeting would be interesting and mutually of value. We will organize face-to-face meetings with researchers or industry representatives (similar to face-to-face brokerage events held in ICT proposer’s days, with the only difference that project partners will match participants according to their specific interests, niche industry, applied research or innovation, needs and challenges, instead of participants matching themselves).
- ‘**I bring the idea, you bring the business**’ will invite participants from the ICT research community to engage with serial entrepreneurs and business angels who will form commercial partnerships to stimulate commercialisation activities. The event will begin with the careful selection of attendees from previous participants and recruitment of serial entrepreneurs and business angels within the partners’ extensive network.

Invited stakeholder will have expertise in several business-related areas, like business development, IPR, marketing, financing/funding, legal advice, etc. These experts, together with MERLIN partners, will help participants performing the next steps of their commercialization road in fields like user testing, finding an incubator/partners, or developing a growth strategy, to mention a few objectives.

Pitching will play a very important role in both types of meetups, given that it is a very important skill that has to be developed by MERLIN participants if they want to participate in business events. For this, we will accommodate some pitching sessions and training with selected participants to guide and correct them while they are working on their pitch deck. Also, since the both meetups have different objectives, we will prepare two pitch decks as a guide for the participants taking part in each meetup, so they know the main points they have to present and discuss during the pitching session, and they have enough time to prepare them properly before the meetups take place.

The meetups, and specially the posterior initiatives and activities performed by the participants, will be key to select and invite MERLIN participants to entrepreneurship related events held in Europe in the context of Startup Europe, or similar events. Their participation in these events can be key for the growing of the researchers, and can be an inflection point for them, helping them taking the next step for successfully commercializing their research results.

Two feedback questionnaires have been created: one for MERLIN partners, and another one for the meetup participants (both selected researchers and invited stakeholders). Their opinion will be very valuable to improve this activity and make it more fruitful. These questionnaires are shown in the annex available at this end of this document.

Both activities will have a similar structure, as described in the following sections. Two meetups per year will be organized by each partner, where the most promising workshop participants will be invited to attend, adding to a total of 16 editions. In order to facilitate the attendance of the participants and the invited stakeholders to the meetups, they will last two or three ours at most, and they will be scheduled on the evening.

2.1. Organization procedure for meetups

Since meetups are a very important activity for achieving MERLIN objectives, and since they will involve not only project participants but also third parties (investors, mentors, staff from transfer offices, other entrepreneurs and stakeholders of the entrepreneurial ecosystem), it is mandatory to think carefully about their structure and to organize them properly. For this, the following activities define the preparation and running of each meetup and should be carried out by each partner:

- 1) Ask participants about their willingness to participate in the meetups, as well as their needs and expectations, to help us invite stakeholders of the local entrepreneurial ecosystem.
- 2) Select venue and date, and invite stakeholders from the local entrepreneurial ecosystem based on the answers to the questionnaire.
- 3) Run meetup.
- 4) Collect feedback from participants and agreements reached after the meetups.

2.2. Agenda for the meetups and description of the activities

The agenda for both meetups would be similar, since their objectives are basically the same. Total expected length of three to four hours.

- 1) **Welcome**, with a presentation of the session, the project and the invited participants, both researchers and stakeholders.
- 2) **Invited speaker**, who will talk about a topic related to the session and his/her expertise for 15-20 min, and will encourage participants to continue developing and exploiting their research results.
- 3) **Pitching activity**, where the participants will present themselves and their ideas, using the pitch decks developed for them (more information on this on the next sections). All selected participants will be encouraged to participate in this pitching activity.
- 4) **Additional activity**, selected depending on the concrete meetup, the experience of the partner, the availability of stakeholders and their opinion, and the results obtained previously from running it.
- 5) **Meetup close**
- 6) **Networking**

Some of the activities that can be planned for bullet point 4, “Additional activity”, are the following. Not all of them will apply for both meetups and for all partners, who may select one over others, and may even repeat the one they think work best in more than one meetup. Some activities may need previous work, for instance, scheduling interviews.

- **Speed dating**, with some facilitating questions to start conversation. “Speed dating” is a formalized matchmaking process whose purpose is to encourage meeting a large number of new people in a very short period of time, and the objective is that participants can meet and talk about their needs with different actors of the entrepreneurial ecosystem who can help them.
- **Pre-arranged meetings**: based on answers to previous questionnaires and the needs of the invited stakeholders, some meetings could be pre-arranged to discuss specific topics.

2.3. General information about “Match-making” meetup

Duration of the workshop: 4 hours

Optimal number of participants: from 20 to 30

Target groups: Junior and senior researchers, PhD students on their last years and post-doc with research results, but also mentors, business angels, incubator staff, potential partners, and other stakeholders of the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Target group needs identified: participants want to commercialize their products / research findings by creating a startup/spinoff, but need help and support from the entrepreneurial ecosystem to do so. They also need to expand their network of contacts.

Key skills to be acquired: mainly pitching and social skills for successfully exploiting their research results.

The main goals of the meetup:

- To help participants practice their pitching skills.
- To widen their network of contacts and get to know other stakeholders of the entrepreneurial ecosystem.
- To reach some agreements and collaborations with attendees.

The main requirements for the venue: computer, projector, projector screen, able to seat 30-40 people. Have space for networking and, optionally, some quiet space for talking.

2.4. General information about “I bring the idea” meetup

Duration of the workshop: 4 hours

Optimal number of participants: from 20 to 30

Target groups: Junior and senior researchers, PhD students on their last years and post-doc with research results, but also serial entrepreneurs, potential partners, staff from transfer offices, and other stakeholders of the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Target group needs identified: participants want a third party to exploit and commercialize the results of their research, and are mostly looking for partners and IPR/legal advice.

Key skills to be acquired: mainly pitching and social skills for successfully exploiting their research results.

The main goals of the meetup:

- To help participants practice their pitching skills.
- To widen their network of contacts and get to know other stakeholders of the entrepreneurial ecosystem.
- To reach some agreements and collaborations with attendees.

The main requirements for the venue: computer, projector, projector screen, able to seat 30-40 people. Have space for networking and, optionally, some quiet space for talking.

3. Pitching activity

Seeking to help ICT researchers / innovators to prepare good Pitch-deck presentations and to present their ideas / products successfully, the trainings on how to prepare successful pitch will be included in one of the Workshop (additional 1 hour to the one of the Workshop's will be added). During these trainings, the main principles, tips of the preparation of the successful investment and product development pitch will be presented.

Trainings will include the main Pitch-deck do's:

- tell a story and engage people emotionally,
- include the main information needed (introduction, team, problem, advantages, solution, product, traction, market, competition, business model, investing, contact),
- limit each slide to expressing one idea,
- prepare to make a great first impression,
- show the people behind your idea,
- keep a consistent look in presentation,
- know your metrics better than anyone.

Trainings will include the main Pitch-deck don't's:

- don't make it too long,

- don't read word by word from your script,
- don't create text-rich, picture-poor presentation,
- don't come unprepared,
- don't use too many bullet points, etc.

Furthermore, those ICT researchers / innovators willing to participate in the meetups and to present their idea to the broader audience (this information will be spread in the previous Workshops) will be able to receive consultations / advices of mentors regarding the preparation of the pitches (Skype call meetings with the representatives of mentors will be assigned to those who will need further consultations, advices).

In order to ensure, that only the good quality pitches will be presented during the meetups, all the meetups participants willing to participate in the Pitch-deck will be asked to send the pitch prepared beforehand. In case of some changes needed, the ICT researchers / innovators receive consultations and comments.

3.1. Pitch-decks: goals and target groups

Although the format and the structure of the Pitch-decks (detailed description provided in the following section) is very similar for both of the Pitch-decks, the goals and the target groups are different.

The main goals of the pitch-decks:

- **The goal of the investment Pitch-deck** – to allow ICT researchers, innovators directly engage with ICT related serial entrepreneurs and business angels who could become prospective clients, partners, investors and will let to stimulate commercialization activities (pitch-deck will be organized during the "Matchmaking" event).
- **The goal of the innovative product Pitch-deck** – to allow ICT researchers, innovators directly engage with ICT industry representatives, technology transfer leads who could become prospective partners in further product development and commercialization process (pitch-deck will be organized during the "I bring the idea" meetup).

Target groups (players and jury members) of the pitch-decks:

- **Investment Pitch-deck players:** ICT researchers, innovators having their own product developed (or ready to be developed) and seeking to commercialize it and / or scale up, thus searching for investors and establishing startups (pitch-deck will be organized during the "Matchmaking" event).
- **Investment Pitch-deck jury:** ICT related serial entrepreneurs and business angels who could become prospective clients, partners, investors and will let to stimulate commercialization activities pitch-deck will be organized during the "Matchmaking" event).
- **Innovative product Pitch-deck players:** ICT researchers, innovators having their own product development idea / developed (partly developed) products and seeking to finalize the development of the innovative product pitch-deck will be organized during the "I bring the idea" meetup).
- **Innovative product Pitch-deck jury:** ICT industry representatives, technology transfer leads who could become prospective partners, clients and will let to stimulate further product development activities (pitch-deck will be organized during the "I bring the idea" meetup).

3.2. Structure of the Pitch-decks

Both Pitch-decks will start with an introduction of the goals of each Pitch-deck (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1 The goal of the investment Pitch-decks

Investment Pitch-deck is a key part of fundraising toolkit

The goal of the investment Pitch-deck – to allow ICT researchers, innovators directly engage with ICT related serial entrepreneurs and business angels who could become prospective clients, partners, investors and will let to stimulate commercialization activities.

Figure 2 The goal of the innovative product Pitch-decks

Innovative product Pitch-deck is a key part of further product development

The goal of the innovative product Pitch-deck – to allow ICT researchers, innovators directly engage with ICT industry representatives, technology transfer leads who could become prospective partners in further product development and commercialization process.

After the participants are introduced with the goal of the Pitch-deck, the target groups of players (presenters) and jury members involved in the Pitch-deck session will be presented (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Players and jury in innovative products Pitch-decks

Players and jury

- **Innovative product Pitch-deck players:** ICT researchers, innovators having their own product development idea / developed (partly developed) products and seeking to to finalize the development of the innovative product.
- **Innovative product Pitch-deck jury:** ICT industry representatives, technology transfer leads who could become prospective partners, clients and will let to stimulate further product development activities.

After the target groups of Pitch-deck will be presented, the general information about the Pitch-deck will be provided:

- Length of the Pitch-deck (1 hour);
- Number of players (presenters) (7);
- Number of presentations (pitches) to be presented (7);
- Number of questions / answers session to be organized (7).

Figure 4 General information about Pitch-decks

General information

- 7 players

- 7 Pitch-decks

- 7 Questions / answers sessions

After the general information will be presented, the participants of the events will get acquired with the information about the main rules to be followed during the Pitch-decks:

- No questions during the presentation (only after);
- Pitch-deck judging criteria: formal and content;
- Scoring Sheets filled by Judges and presentation of the evaluation results.

The main purpose of the introduction of the rules for the Pitch-deck is to let the participants to understand the rules of the Pitch-deck (pitching - evaluation according to the criteria, etc.), to encourage participants to ask questions after each pitch (but not interrupting presenters during the presentation as the presenter will have limited time for its presentation).

Figure 5 Rules for the Pitch-decks

Rules for the Pitch-deck

- No questions during the Pitch-deck presentation (only after)

- Pitch-deck judging criteria: formal and content

- Scoring Sheets filled by Judges and presentation of the evaluation results

Participants of the Pitch-deck will also get information about the formal criteria of Pitch-deck evaluation:

- Pitch-deck should be prepared beforehand using PowerPoint, Prezi or similar tool,
- Pitch-deck length – max 10 minutes,
- Maximum 15 slides (or less – not more).

Figure 6 Pitch-decks formal evaluation criteria

Pitch-deck judging: formal criteria

○ Pitch-deck prepared beforehand using PowerPoint, Prezi or similar tool

○ Pitch-deck length – max 10 minutes

○ Maximum 15 slides (or less - not more)

Furthermore, participants will receive information about the content criteria of Pitch-deck evaluation (what kind of information the pitch should contain):

- **Introduction.** Who are you and why you're here?
- **Team.** Show the people behind the idea and briefly describe their role.
- **Problem.** What problem are you trying to solve? Is it really a problem?
- **Advantages.** What makes your solution special? How are you different from others?
- **Solution.** Describe how are you planning to solve the problem.
- **Product.** How does your product or service actually work? Show some examples.
- **Traction.** Traction means having a measurable set of customers that serves to prove a potential.
- **Market.** Know, or at least attempt to predict, the size of your target market.
- **Competition.** What are the alternative solutions to the problem you are trying to solve?
- **Business model.** How are you planning to make money? Show a schedule when you expect revenues to pour in.
- **Investing.** What is your planned budget? What kind of money are you looking for?
- **Contact.** Leave your contact details and let people know how to reach you quickly.

Figure 7 Pitch-decks content evaluation criteria

Pitch deck judging: content criteria

After presenting the Pitch-deck evaluation criteria, the main principles of the further evaluation process (which will be implemented by jury members) will be presented. Each jury member will fill the evaluation sheet while evaluating each content criteria and assigning points. Points from 1 to 5 will be assigned to the each of the content criteria:

- 1-2 points for the insecure, insufficient and non-satisfactory performance,
- 3 points for the good performance,
- 4-5 points for the excellent performance with none or few inessential shortcomings.

Weights to the each of the criteria will be added. After the evaluation will be finished the total points will be counted and the results (from all jury members) will be summed up.

Figure 8 Evaluation of the Pitch-decks

Evaluation of the Pitch-decks

Points from 1 to 5 will be assigned to the each of the content criteria

Weights will be added for the specific criteria's

Total points per Pitch-deck will be counted

The winner Pitch-deck will be selected and announced

Finally, after presenting Pitch-deck evaluation process and criteria to be evaluated, the judges (Figure 9) and the players (Figure 10) will be presented briefly.

Figure 9 Meet the Judges of the Pitch-decks

Figure 10 Meet the Players of the Pitch-decks

After each pitch, the question and answer session will take a place (jury members as well as other participants will be able to ask the presenter (player) some questions). After all presentations and questions and answers sessions will be finished, the jury will announce the winner.

4. Conclusions

This document has described the organization of the two kinds of meetups that will be run in the context of MERLIN project, 16 editions in total in two years. Their purpose is to encourage promising researcher to continue their journey to commercializing their research results, as well as introduce them to the local and European entrepreneurship environments, and improve their pitching skills. Our hope is that, the more people they meet and the more they know about the entrepreneurship ecosystem, the more likely they will be to start their own startup/spinoff.

The organization and structure of the meetups may be slightly altered as they are run, based on the participants and partner feedback, but their essence (help MERLIN participants get to know the local and European entrepreneurship ecosystems and the opportunities they offer) won't be altered.

FEEDBACK REPORT AFTER MERLIN MEETUP - PARTNER

Name of meetup:		Date:	
Place:			
Partner:		# of participants / stakeholders	
Feedback regarding timing and agenda			
Feedback regarding participants engagement			
What has been the "brightest point"?			
What has been the "muddiest point"?			
Recommendations			

FEEDBACK REPORT AFTER MERLIN MEETUP - PARTICIPANT

Name of meetup:		Date:	
Place:			
MERLIN participant or invited stakeholder?:			
Feedback regarding timing and agenda			
What has been the "brightest point"?			
What has been the "muddiest point"?			
Recommendations			

